

Determination of Stability Constants of 4-(*o*-Methoxyphenyl)thiosemicarbazide Complexes with Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Oxovanadium(IV)

S. B. SAXENA* and Y. K. AGARWAL

Department of Applied Chemistry, Madhav Institute of Technology and Science, Gwalior-474 005

Manuscript received 30 May 1983, revised 3 January 1985, accepted 29 April 1985

Potentiometric studies on metal complexes of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and VO^{2+} with 4-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)thiosemicarbazide have been investigated. The proton-ligand dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ and at three ionic concentrations, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 *M* in 40 : 60 percent (v/v) ethanol-water medium. The stoichiometry of the metal and ligand interaction was found to be 1 : 2 from Job's continuous variation method.

THE stability constants of the chelates of 4-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)thiosemicarbazide have so far not been reported with metal ions studied. We have, therefore, thought it proper to study the stabilities of the chelates of 4-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)thiosemicarbazide with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and VO^{2+} metal ions. It will be in fitness of things to mention here that the above semicarbazide possesses antitubercular^{1,2} and antifungal activity³ *in vitro*. The transition metal ions used in the present investigations are also of biological importance⁴.

Experimental

Systronics digital pH meter with glass electrode and calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements. The ligand 4-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)thiosemicarbazide was prepared in the laboratory and recrystallised from ethanol⁵. The purity of ligand was ascertained by elemental analysis and m.p. (154°).

All chemicals used were B.D.H. analytical grade. The medium of titration was ethanol-water 40 : 60 (v/v) mixture. Distilled water, redistilled over potassium permanganate, was used throughout the investigations. Potassium chloride was added to maintain the different ionic strengths. The titration was carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen gas.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against carbonate free potassium hydroxide (0.01 *M*) solution.

- (i) 5 ml 0.01 *M* HCl + 5 ml 0.10 *M* KCl + 40 ml 40% ethanol-water mixture.
- (ii) 5 ml 0.01 *M* HCl + 5 ml 0.10 *M* KCl + 20 ml ligand (0.001 *M*) + 30 ml 40% ethanol-water mixture.

- (iii) 5 ml 0.01 *M* HCl + 5 ml 0.10 *M* KCl + 10 ml ligand (0.001 *M*) + 2 ml metal + 28 ml 40% ethanol-water mixture.

All titrations were performed in duplicate to test the reproducibility. The experimental method of Bjerrum⁶, Calvin⁷ pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti^{8,9} was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

From Fig. 1 it is evident that stoichiometry of complexes is 1 : 2. It may be pointed out that the ligand used in this study did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions. This was indicated by the rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after 1 h.

From the titration curves using the solutions (i) and (ii) $\bar{n}H$ values at various *B* values (*pH* meter readings), were calculated. The minimum value "2" for $\bar{n}H$ was obtained which indicates that two-step dissociation of the ligand is possible. The values of pK_1H and pK_2H were evaluated by half-integral method, as well as from the plot of $\log \bar{n}H/(1-\bar{n}H)$ vs *pH* and $\log (2-\bar{n}H)/(\bar{n}H-1)$ vs *pH*. Both these values agree well. \bar{n} and pL values were calculated from the titration curve of solutions (ii) and (iii). The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of metal complex ion equilibria. From this $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were evaluated by half-integral method. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

It is also evident from the positive values of $\Delta \log kH$ (Table 1) that the first protonation of the ligand occurs in steps. Further, the negative values of $\Delta \log K$ indicate that 1 : 2 species is rather more

TABLE 1—STEPWISE AND OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES OF 4-(*o*-METHOXYPHENYL)THIOSEMICARBAZIDE WITH SOME BIVALENT METAL IONS

Temp. = 37 ± 0.1°		Standard deviation σ = 0.03				Method
Ionic strength (μ) M	Cations	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ⁿ (overall)	Δ log K	
0.00*	H ⁺	11.70	9.30	21.00	-2.4	b
	Ni ²⁺	4.05	4.05	7.65	0.00	b
	Co ²⁺	3.90	4.05	7.72	+0.15	b
	VO ²⁺	3.52	3.55	7.58	+0.03	b
0.05	H ⁺	11.45	8.24	19.69	-3.21	b
		11.10	8.30	19.40		a
	Ni ²⁺	3.80	3.90	7.70	+0.10	b
		3.79	3.88	7.67		a
	Co ²⁺	3.83	3.90	7.73	+0.02	b
		3.79	3.95	7.74		a
0.10	H ⁺	11.26	6.88	18.14	-4.38	b
		11.01	7.00	18.01		a
	Ni ²⁺	3.80	3.90	7.70	+0.10	b
		3.79	3.91	7.70		a
	Co ²⁺	3.81	3.88	7.69	+0.07	b
		3.81	3.94	7.75		a
0.20	H ⁺	11.23	7.66	18.89	-3.57	b
		11.80	7.95	19.75		a
	Ni ²⁺	3.79	3.89	7.68	+0.10	b
		3.78	3.92	7.70		a
	Co ²⁺	3.79	3.87	7.66	+0.08	b
		3.78	3.86	7.64		a
	VO ²⁺	3.69	3.85	7.54	+0.16	b
		3.75	3.85	7.60		a

^a Interpolation at 1/2 n̄ values. ^b Interpolation at various n̄ values. *Thermodynamic stability constant.

stable than 1 : 1. This is also in agreement with results of Job's method of continuous variation (Fig. 1).

The thermodynamic stability of the complexes was obtained by extrapolation of various stability constants at different ionic strengths to zero ionic strength. The data is recorded in Table 1.

The order of the metal-ligand interaction is well in agreement with Murakami order¹⁰ for cobalt and nickel.

The overall stability constant for Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and VO²⁺ complexes of 4-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)thiosemicarbazide are as follows,

Fig. 1. Job's method of continuous variation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. P. Katrolia of Defence Research and Development Establishment, Gwalior for help, and indebted to Prof. K. K. Shrivastava, Principal, M.I.T.S., Gwalior for providing facilities. One of the authors (Y.K.A.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. N. P. BUU-HOI, N. D. XUONG, J. D. GAZAVE, Z. NAM and C. T. LONG, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, 50, 13916.
2. C. RUNTI and F. COLLINO, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, 57, 7137.
3. T. ZSOLNAI, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1962, 11, 271 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, 57, 6431).
4. A. FURST, in "Chemistry of Chelation in Cancer", ed. C. C. THOMAS, Springfield, 1963.
5. L. EUGENE, C. N. PILLA and R. D. HITES, *Can J. Chem.*, 1957, 35, 832.
6. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. HASE & Sons, Copenhagen, 1941, p. 39.
7. A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds", Prentice-Hall, New York, 1952.
8. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
9. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
10. Y. MURAKAMI, K. NAKAMURA and M. TOKUNAGA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1963, 36, 669.